

GLC Studies in some Seed Oils

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Cassia fistula (Leguminosae), *Nigella sativa* (Ranunculaceae) and *Acaccia catechu* (Leguminosae) seeds are found in abundance in our region. Some workers^{1,2} have worked on these seed oils from other regions but so far complete fatty acid composition has not been successfully determined. The present work determines, for the first time, all the fatty acids present in these seed oils.

The seeds were obtained from Kamala Seeds, Nagpur. These powdered seeds were extracted by n-hexane. The oils were dried and converted into the respective fatty acid methyl esters³. These esters were analysed on a Perkin-Elmer 1.54 gas chromatograph, equipped with a computer having a flame ionisation detector at 280° and a column consisting of 15% EGSS-X on Chromosorb-W (40–60 mesh). The other conditions were as follows: column temperature 200°, injection port temperature 300°, chart speed 60 cm h⁻¹ and nitrogen flow rate 60 ml min⁻¹. The fatty acids were identified by comparison of the relative retention times⁴ of the standard methyl esters (Analabs). The fatty acid compositions of the seed oils are presented in Table 1. Earlier results on these seed oils are also reported.

The earlier work by Ansari *et al.*¹ did not report the presence of myristic, myristoleic, arachi-

donic and behenic acids, which are reported in the present work. Also there is no report on the presence of myristic, myristolic, arachidonic and behenic acids. So the present work is the first report on these fatty acids in *C. fistula* seed oil.

TABLE 1—FATTY ACID COMPOSITION OF SEED OILS*

Fatty acids (wt. %)	Seed Oils					
	<i>C. fistula</i>		<i>N. sativa</i>		<i>A. catechu</i>	
	(a)	(b)	(a)	(b)	(a)	(b)
Myristic	0.12	—	0.19	1.80	0.14	—
Myristoleic	0.09	—	—	—	0.03	—
Palmitic	17.03	20.30	12.46	17.12	20.43	21.00
Palmitoleic	0.02	0.30	0.20	—	0.18	0.90
Stearic	3.17	4.20	1.81	6.08	2.63	2.20
Oleic	18.18	19.50	24.46	26.24	38.85	28.26
Linoleic	56.99	50.50	57.63	48.76	35.70	36.09
Linolenic	3.30	5.20	0.57	—	0.92	1.30
Arachidic	—	—	0.19	—	—	—
Arachidonic	0.34	—	2.49	—	0.02	—
Behenic	—	—	—	—	0.95	—
Euricic	—	—	—	—	—	—
Lignoceric	0.07	—	—	—	0.15	—
Unknown	—	—	—	—	—	10.34

*All values are means of triplicate analysis.
(a) = Present work, (b) = Earlier report.

Earlier Mustafa *et al.*² showed the fatty acid

NOTES

composition of *N. sativa* seed oil. Myristoleic, linoleic, arachidic and arachidonic acids which have not been found earlier are reported in the present work. Unusually arachidonic acid has been found to be present in good amounts (2.49%) as compared to the earlier results.

The earlier study by Mustafa *et al.*² on *A. catechu* seed oil did not report the presence of myristoleic, arachidonic behenic and lignoceric acids, which have been identified in the present work. The amount of unknown acids has been reduced to nil in this work. Arachidonic acid was found to be present, but in it is totally absent in our investigation.

C. fistula and *A. catechu* seed oils belong to the same (Leguminosae) family but there are fluctuations in the fatty acids quantitatively even though they remain more or less the same qualitatively.

Nearly (upto 0.07%) all the fatty acids in the

seed oils have been identified and quantified in the present work. *A. catechu* and *C. fistula* seed oils have comparable contents of linoleic acids (50%).

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